

CAREER PROGRESSION OF THE MASTER OF ARTS IN EDUCATION GRADUATES OF TOMAS CLAUDIO COLLEGES

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Career Progression of the Master of Arts in Education Graduates of Tomas Claudio Colleges

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Abstract

The study aimed to find out the level of career progression of the Master of Arts in Education (MAEd) graduates of Tomas Claudio Colleges from the School Year 2018 to 2021. The respondents of the study were the 268 or 50% of the graduates of Master of Arts in Education of Tomas Claudio Colleges from the School Year 2018 to 2021. Descriptive survey research design was used in the study and utilized researcher-made questionnaire-checklist as the main instrument in gathering the needed data. The study revealed that most of the respondents are 30-39 years old, female and married. Most of them are graduates in 2019 with Educational Attainment as major of specialization. They are also holders of Master's degree, Teacher III and have served for 1-5 years. Graduates of Master of Arts in Education are always aware on the importance of personal growth, professional development and professional engagement in their career progression. There is no significant difference between the level of career progression of the Master of Arts in Education graduates in terms of their sex, civil status, year graduated and major of specialization with respect to personal growth, professional development and professional engagement. However, it is significant when they are grouped according to their age, educational attainment, position title and length of service with respect to professional development. The study concluded that teachers' sex, civil status, year graduated and major of specialization do not affect their career progression as graduates of Master of Arts in Education. However, when it comes to their age, educational attainment, position title and length of service, it is significant in their professional development. It was recommended that school administrators may give recognition to their teachers who have the best performance to keep them motivated and inspired in providing their focused and committed services.

Keywords: *career progression, MAEd, descriptive*

Introduction

Education plays an essential role in shaping an individual's career. It placed at the epicenter of professional transformation that serve as an equalizer and contributory to the humanization of this world. In the Asia-Pacific region, which includes the Philippines, has been experiencing rapid changes in the economic, political, technological, cultural, and social arena. These adjustments have significant implications for the reengineering of the present educational system.

In this new normal, education is still the root cause for any considerable transformation, which takes place on the different dimension of person's entity and help to adapt with the varying environment. Certainly, it is both personally and professionally an indispensable element that provide a powerful instrument to reshape and redesign the future of every individual. The level of education attained helps people to fulfill its dream, satisfaction, earn recognition, and respect in the society.

Hence, the necessity for career progression is imperative. It is the act of moving forward in teaching profession and more than "climbing the ladder" at work. Progressing in a chosen career does not always mean of getting promoted or securing a more highly paid role. It can take in many forms, including being awarded more responsibility within the existing role, moving to a different sector or functional line, taking on new challenges, and increasing skillset through different training and developmental opportunities.

Guided by the fundamental law of the State, statutory rules, and uphold the dignity of the teaching profession, the researchers believed that several conditions and events surfaced called for continuous improvement and career renewal. Likewise, educators are never finished with their learning after earning a certain degree. Rather, teacher's knowledge, skills, behaviors, and attitudes must continue to develop and improve throughout their professional careers.

Likewise, the researchers recognize the influential changes brought about by various national and international frameworks such as the K to 12 reform, ASEAN integration, globalization, and the changing character of the 21st century learners which requires an intensive assessment of the major issues and concerns of the teachers. At present, a new challenge on the teaching career arises from the national adoption and implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) in the continuing professional development and advancement of teachers based on the principle of lifelong learning.

Furthermore, the researchers having been part of the administration and faculty members of the Graduate Studies Program (GSP) of Tomas Claudio Colleges (TCC) were motivated to exert their effort and find out through formal investigation the profile and other interrelated facts that would provide information.

Research Questions

The study aimed to find out the level of career progression of the Master of Arts in Education (MAEd) graduates of Tomas Claudio Colleges from the School Year 2018 to 2021. Specifically, it sought answers to the following sub-problems:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. year graduated;
 - 1.5. major of specialization;
 - 1.6. educational attainment;
 - 1.7. position title; and
 - 1.8. length of service?
2. What is the level of career progression of the Master of Arts in Education graduates as perceived by themselves with respect to:
 - 2.1. personal growth;
 - 2.2. professional development; and
 - 2.3. professional engagement?
3. Is there a significant difference between the level of career progression of the Master of Arts in Education graduates as perceived by themselves with respect to the different aspects in terms of their profile?

Literature Review

Duke (2020) stated that teachers may not be professional and they need to be professionalized. However, from time to time, resources and trainings are far from being responsive to their needs and their professional roles. Sometimes, their training may even neglect due to limited financial resources. For a satisfactory and effective teacher training program, it is essential that teachers, as the most valuable human resource in the educational systems, should improve their teaching skills.

In addition, Wolk et. al., (2015), cited that there are many factors that can influence whether a highly talented staff member will build a career within an institution or use it as a stepping stone. This article defines and explores the notions of developing career paths and succession planning and why they are critical human capital investment strategies in retaining the highest performers in advancement divisions.

The article discusses how developing career paths and engaging in succession planning is a long-term human capital investment with a powerful return.

Relatively, Lecaroz, (2018), stressed that professional development refers to a variety of activities, both formal and informal, designed for the personal and professional growth of teachers and administrators. It includes individual development, as well as curriculum writing, peer collaboration, study groups, peer coaching or mentoring, classroom visitation, attendance of conference, action research, publication of papers, etc. professional development activities are varied because they have to serve teachers and administrators not only at different levels of instruction or management but also different points in their career development.

As stipulated by Wichadee (2012), Professional development is deemed necessary for university teachers at all levels, as it helps to enhance teaching quality. The results indicate that the overall mean score of Thai university teachers' professional development was at a moderate level, and the factors of gender, academic title, degree and job responsibility were not related to professional development.

Moreso, the study of Dialoke and Wabara (2017) examined career development and employee commitment of selected higher institutions in Abia State, Nigeria. The findings of the study revealed that mentoring and job enrichment enhances employee commitment in the higher institutions. The study concluded that career development measured in terms of mentoring and job enrichment improves employee commitment in the higher institutions.

The study recommended that human resource managers should incorporate mentoring and job enrichment in their functions as factors that can improve career development of their employees which in turn increases their commitment to achieve organizational goals.

The tracer study of Cagasan (2017) was conducted to determine the employment characteristics and job experiences of the graduates of Visayas State University's (VSU) graduate degree programs, and feedback on their educational experiences in the university. Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that VSU has successfully attained its goal of developing manpower which can provide leadership in addressing the development needs specifically of the Visayas region. The degree programs pursued by the graduate students in VSU were also able to help improve the skills of the students and the employment status of the graduates.

Furthermore, the study of Aligacion and Dimaranan (2018) focused on identifying the demographic profile, the career advancement, and the level of self-efficacy of the graduates of Cavite State University General Trias City Campus (CvSU-GTC). The result between demographic profile and career advancement are not significantly related in terms of age, gender, occupation, job status, year in service, honor received, and special awards received to professional exam since the result is greater than the p-value.

On the other hand, there is significant relationship in terms of civil status, program and year graduated to professional exam since the result is less than the p-value.

Methodology

Research Design

The study used the descriptive method of research utilizing the researcher-made questionnaire-checklist as tool to gather the needed data. To Ardales (2018), descriptive research is concerned with conditions and relationships that exists, practices that prevail, beliefs and process that are going on, effects or trends that are being developed. This method helped the researchers to the find out the level of career progression of the Master of Arts in Education (MAEd) graduates of Tomas Claudio Colleges.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were 268 or 50% of the graduates of Master of Arts in Education (MAEd) of Tomas Claudio Colleges from the School Year 2018 to 2021. Simple random sampling was employed to the MAEd graduates to have them an equal probability of being included as respondents of the study. They were described in terms of age, sex, civil status, year graduated, major of specialization, educational attainment, position title, and length of service.

Instrument

A researcher-made questionnaire-checklist was used as the main instrument in gathering the needed data. Significant part of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) serves as guide in the development of the research instrument particular Domain 6 – Community Linkages and Professional Engagement and Domain 7 – Personal Growth and Professional Development.

Part I dealt with the personal profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, year graduated, major of specialization, educational attainment, position title, and length of service. Part II dealt on the level of career progression of the Master of Arts in Education (MAEd) graduates with respect to personal growth, professional development, and professional engagement. Each aspect consists of 10 items with a total of 30 items.

Procedure

The researcher followed a Gantt Chart of Activities as guide in the conduct of the present study. This includes the formulation of research problems, title defense, colloquium up to the revision of the manuscript and submission of the final copy. Different steps were undertaken including the incorporation of the comments and suggestions of the panel members to quality assure the content of the study. Immediately after the research proposal defense, validation of the research instrument was done. Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the Office of the Dean of the Graduate Studies Program.

The questionnaire-checklist was administered by the researchers to the respondents through Google survey form in compliance with the health and safety protocols on the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) for the Management of Infectious Diseases. Likewise, Republic Act No. 10173 otherwise known as Data Privacy Act was also considered to preserve the confidentiality of the answers of the respondents. After the retrieval, the data were encoded, processed, and treated with appropriate statistical tools utilizing the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Based on the interpreted data, the summary of findings, conclusion and recommendations were formulated.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Age, Sex, Civil Status, Year Graduated, Major of Specialization, Educational Attainment, Position Title and Length of Service

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Selected Variables

<i>Age</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>R</i>
50 years old and above	10	3.7	4
40 – 49 years old	66	24.6	3
30 - 39 years old	111	41.4	1
20 – 29 years old	81	30.2	2
<i>Sex</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>R</i>
Male	25	9.3	2
Female	243	90.7	1
<i>Civil Status</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>R</i>
Single	89	33.2	2
Married	170	63.4	1
Widow/Widower	6	2.2	3
Separated	3	1.1	4
<i>Year Graduated</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>R</i>
Year 2021	76	28.4	3
Year 2020	84	31.3	2

Year 2019	108	40.3	1
Major of Specialization	f	%	R
MAED-Educational Management	257	95.9	1
MAED-Guidance Counseling	11	4.1	2
Educational Attainment	f	%	R
With Ph. D. / Ed. Units	93	34.7	2
Master's Degree	175	65.3	1
Position Title	f	%	R
Master Teacher II	11	4.1	3
Master Teacher I	33	12.3	2
Teacher III	216	80.6	1
Teacher I	8	3.0	4
Length of Service			
25 – 30 years	6	2.2	6
21 – 25 years	9	3.4	5
16 - 20 years	24	9.0	4
11 – 15 years	32	11.9	3
6 – 10 years	79	29.5	2
1 - 5 years	118	44.0	1
Total	268	100.0	

As indicated in the table, in terms of the age of the respondents, most of them are 30 – 39 years old at 41.4% while 3.7% of them are 50 years old and above. It is female dominated at 90.7% since the male respondents got 9.3%.

In terms of their civil status, majority of them are married at 63.4% while 1.1% of them are separated. Most of the Master of Arts in Education (MAEd) students graduated in the year 2019 at 40.3% while 28.4% from the year 2021. Likewise, as to their major of specialization, majority of them are graduates of MAED-Educational Management at 95.9% while 4.1% is in MAED-Guidance Counseling. It is also noted that as to their educational attainment, majority of them are master’s degree holders at 65.3% while 34.7% have units in Ph.D. / Ed.D. Moreover, in terms of their position title, majority of them are holders of Teacher III position at 80.6% while 3.0% of them are in Teacher I position. In addition, most of the teachers have 1 – 5 years teaching experience at 44.0% while 2.2% from 25 – 30 years.

Level of Career Progression of the Master of Arts in Education Graduates as Perceived by Themselves with Respect to Personal Growth, Professional Development and Professional Engagement

As shown in the next table, the level of career progression of the Master of Arts in Education graduates as perceived by themselves with respect to personal growth is found to be Always at an overall mean of 4.57. This means that weighted means of all the descriptions are close together since all of them are verbally interpreted as Always. As graduates of Master of Arts in Education, teachers exhibit behaviors that support their relationships with their family, friends, and relatives, and they reflect on their self-evaluation process to build their strengths and address their weaknesses.

Table 2. *Computed Weighted Mean on the Level of Career Progression of the Master of Arts in Education Graduates as Perceived by Themselves with Respect to Personal Growth*

<i>As graduate of Master of Arts in Education, I...</i>	<i>Personal Growth</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	lives with dignity in all places at all times and recognizes that Almighty God as guide of my own destiny.	4.59	Always	4
2.	applies personal philosophy and accountability on my individual undertakings;	4.56	Always	8
3.	demonstrate behaviors that uphold relations to my family, friends, and relatives.	4.61	Always	2
4.	recognizes that the interest and welfare of my learners are first and foremost the immediate concern.	4.60	Always	3
5.	serves as role model worthy of emulation by my learners and co-teachers.	4.57	Always	6.5
6.	shows courtesy, helpfulness, and sympathy towards school leaders, co-teachers, and other school personnel.	4.53	Always	9.5
7.	establishes and maintains cordial relations with parents, guardians, and other community stakeholders.	4.53	Always	9.5
8.	maintains good reputation with respect to monetary matters and support the financial literacy advocacy.	4.58	Always	5
9.	engages directly or indirectly to legitimate income generation if it does not relate to or adversely affect my teaching work.	4.57	Always	6.5
10.	reflects based on my self-evaluation process to enhance one’s strengths and adjust on limitations.	4.62	Always	1
Overall Mean		4.57	Always	

Findings imply that teachers have high regard in the different opportunities brought by the career progression on their personal growth. By attending graduate education, teachers can do their best to act as learning facilitators. Teachers need to obtain master's degree to maintain their best performance. If teachers acquire the skills required for their job, they will be more effective and productive, which will benefit the school.

This supports the statement of Fajardo (2020) that as the educational system evolves, schools are finding ways to provide quality education to students. Many articles are floating on the internet stating the must 21st century skills of teachers and students. Most teachers keep attending training to improve their skills, especially in Information and Communications Technology (ICT).

Table 3. *Computed Weighted Mean on the Level of Career Progression of the Master of Arts in Education Graduates as Perceived by Themselves with Respect to Professional Development*

<i>As graduate of Master of Arts in Education, I...</i>	<i>Professional Development</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	allocates time to attend to post-graduate studies or doctorate degree courses.	4.62	Always	5
2.	participates to webinar series, conferences, online or face-to-face trainings.	4.67	Always	1
3.	shares instructional expertise through forum, symposium, or workshops.	4.57	Always	9
4.	facilitates school in-service trainings such as learning action cell (LAC) sessions, focused group discussions (FGD), and other local professional gatherings.	4.62	Always	5
5.	evaluates relevant data gathered and processed information for appropriate development of instructional plan.	4.59	Always	8
6.	develops and utilizes a variety of instructional strategies and learning assessments based on the learners' context.	4.63	Always	3
7.	incorporate advance information and communication technology into teaching and learning process.	4.65	Always	2
8.	accepts personal accountability to learners' achievement and performance.	4.54	Always	10
9.	improves teaching performance based on feedback from learners, peers, school leaders, and others.	4.60	Always	7
10.	develops a personal professional improvement plan based on self-reflection or assessment.	4.62	Always	5
Overall Mean		4.61	Always	

As indicated in the table, the level of career progression of the Master of Arts in Education graduates as perceived by themselves with respect to professional development is found to be Always at an overall mean of 4.61. Findings indicate that weighted means of all the descriptions are close together since all of them are verbally interpreted as Always. As graduates of Master of Arts in Education, teachers take part in webinar series, conferences, online or in-person training, and they integrate cutting-edge ICT into the teaching and learning process.

It implies that teachers can keep up on curricular requirements and teaching practices through professional development. Professional development improves teacher's individual skill sets, which boosts the total worth of school's department when it comes to school-wide projects and involvement within the community.

This is in relation with the citations of Lecaroz, (2018) that professional development refers to a variety of activities, both formal and informal, designed for the personal and professional growth of teachers and administrators.

Table 4. *Computed Weighted Mean on the Level of Career Progression of the Master of Arts in Education Graduates as Perceived by Themselves with Respect to Professional Engagement*

<i>As graduate of Master of Arts in Education, I...</i>	<i>Professional Engagement</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	seeks advice concerning specific strategies that encourages support on teaching related concerns.	4.57	Always	3.5
2.	builds relation to parents, guardians, private individuals, and local government officials to participate with different instructional undertakings.	4.55	Always	6.5
3.	leads professional colleagues and wider school community to strengthen involvement in the educative process.	4.55	Always	6.5
4.	strengthen educational networks to both internal and external stakeholders that maintain effective learning environment within the school community contexts.	4.49	Often	10
5.	keeps abreast with the trends and recent developments in the field of education.	4.57	Always	3.5
6.	conducts action or basic research that create alternative instructional solutions and propose recommendations on policy formulation.	4.57	Always	3.5
7.	subscribes on professional magazines, e-journals, and other reading materials to updates on information and latest developments in the field of teaching.	4.57	Always	3.5
8.	links with professional organizations to generate technical, instructional, and	4.58	Always	1

institutional resources.			
9. involves with other professional institutions that supports teachers' welfare and for sharing best practices in teaching.	4.53	Always	8.5
10. creates teaching environment or quality circle group that advocates a culture of excellence or professional learning community.	4.53	Always	8.5
	Overall Mean	4.55	Always

As reflected in the table, the level of career progression of the Master of Arts in Education graduates as perceived by themselves with respect to professional engagement is found to be Always at an overall mean of 4.55. Findings indicate that weighted means of all the descriptions are close together since almost all of them are verbally interpreted as Always. To generate technical, instructional, and institutional resources, teachers collaborate with professional associations.

This implies that the professional engagement of teachers is essential in developing a good dependable workforce, therefore it is vital to train them and to improve their performance level.

Findings are in relation to the statement of Ancho (2021) that teachers were exposed to webinars and training on online teaching and learning, technological capacity, and mental health.

Table 5. Composite Mean on the Level of Career Progression of the Master of Arts in Education Graduates as Perceived by Themselves with Respect to Different Aspects

Aspect	Overall Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Personal Growth	4.57	Always	2
Professional Development	4.61	Always	1
Professional Engagement	4.55	Always	3
Composite Mean	4.58	Always	

As shown in the table, the composite weighted mean obtained is 4.58 verbally interpreted as Always. First in rank is professional development with weighted mean of 4.61, second in rank is personal growth with weighted mean of 4.57 and last in rank is professional engagement with weighted mean of 4.55. All aspects are verbally interpreted as Always. It could be deduced from the results that as an overall perception leading to the level of career progression of the Master of Arts in Education graduates is found to be Always as evaluated by themselves.

This implies that since they have always been at the center of education, teachers' career progression has been the main concern of the educational system. It is crucial to remember that they must always improve their subject-matter expertise and instructional techniques if they are to make a difference in their students' academic performance.

This supports the statement of Curtiss et. al (2020) that quality teaching also can play a role in improving equity, as several years of outstanding teaching may in fact offset learning deficits of disadvantaged students.

Significant Difference Between the Level of Career Progression of the Master of Arts in Education Graduates as Perceived by Themselves with Respect to the Different Aspects in Terms of Their Profile

Table 6. Result of the F-test on the Significant Difference Between the Level of Career Progression of the Master of Arts in Education Graduates as Perceived by Themselves with Respect to the Different Aspects in Terms of Their Profile

Profile	f-value	p-value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Age				
Personal Growth	2.464	.063	Accepted	Not Significant
Professional Development	3.467	.017	Rejected	Significant
Professional Engagement	.988	.425	Accepted	Not Significant
Sex				
Personal Growth	.204	.652	Accepted	Not Significant
Professional Development	.002	.962	Accepted	Not Significant
Professional Engagement	2.536	.057	Accepted	Not Significant
Civil Status				
Personal Growth	1.276	.283	Accepted	Not Significant
Professional Development	1.205	.308	Accepted	Not Significant
Professional Engagement	.076	.783	Accepted	Not Significant
Year Graduated				
Personal Growth	1.181	.317	Accepted	Not Significant
Professional Development	2.353	.073	Accepted	Not Significant
Professional Engagement	.880	.452	Accepted	Not Significant
Major of Specialization				
Personal Growth	.094	.759	Accepted	Not Significant

Professional Development	.001	.982	Accepted	Not Significant
Professional Engagement	2.103	.100	Accepted	Not Significant
Educational Attainment				
Personal Growth	2.356	.072	Accepted	Not Significant
Professional Development	3.584	.029	Rejected	Significant
Professional Engagement	.939	.333	Accepted	Not Significant
Position Title				
Personal Growth	1.179	.320	Accepted	Not Significant
Professional Development	2.787	.041	Rejected	Significant
Professional Engagement	.573	.565	Accepted	Not Significant
Length of Service				
Personal Growth	1.979	.520	Accepted	Not Significant
Professional Development	2.987	.041	Rejected	Significant
Professional Engagement	1.073	.765	Accepted	Not Significant

The table reflects that the hypothesis on the level of career progression of the Master of Arts in Education graduates as perceived by themselves in terms of sex, civil status, year graduated and major of specialization with respect to personal growth, professional development and professional engagement is accepted since the p-values when associated with the F-values are higher at 0.05 level. However, when grouped according to age, educational attainment, position title and length of service with respect to professional development, the obtained p-values are lower than .05 level, thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

From this result, it can be implied that teachers' sex, civil status, year graduated and major of specialization do not affect their career progression as graduates of Master of Arts in Education. However, when they are grouped according to their age, educational attainment, position title and length of service with respect to professional development, their performance is affected.

These findings are parallel with the statements of Aligacion and Dimaranan (2018) that the result between demographic profile and career advancement are not significantly related in terms of age, gender, occupation, job status, year in service, honor received, and special awards received to professional exam since the result is greater than the p-value.

Conclusions

The study concluded that teachers' sex, civil status, year graduated and major of specialization do not affect their career progression as graduates of Master of Arts in Education. However, when it comes to their age, educational attainment, position title and length of service, it is significant in their professional development.

In the light of the findings, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

School administrators may give recognition to their teachers who have the best performance to keep them motivated and inspired in providing their focused and committed services.

Teachers may be encouraged to attend different educational trainings in order to increase their professional engagement.

Teachers may be encouraged to maintain and improve their career progression in order to improve their abilities.

Teachers can develop their abilities and competencies as learning facilitators for their professional development by participating in seminars and trainings.

The proposed institutional plan is recommended for implementation.

Conduct of similar studies along this area using other variables may be done.

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